

DECOHERENCE FREE SUBSPACE QUBITS ON QUANTUM COMPUTERS*

Kamil WERESZCZYŃSKI¹, Agnieszka MICHALCZUK¹,
Kacper SPACZYŃSKI-KOCIOŁ¹, Krzysztof CYRAN¹

¹ merQlab, Department of Computer Graphics, Vision and Digital Systems,
Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland

Introduction

Decoherence Free Subspace DFS is a notion from the area of quantum mechanics. Let's consider a multidimension quantum system that is, in general, susceptible for a decoherence and other external influences. Certainly, its state is a ray in a Hilbert $\mathcal{H}$ space of the same dimension. According to Lidar and Whaley definition [1], the DFS is such a subspace $\tilde{\mathcal{H}} \subset \mathcal{H}$, that the unitary operators acting on it are pure. The DFS qubits are then a two-dimension system covered in higher dimension spaces. This process can rise as the side-effect of the complex quantum system, like in the case of ion-trap base computation, where the system is the 21 dimension connection of the electric field and ion vibrations projected on two dimension qubit system. Similarly in the superconducting qubits the original space has much more dimension the the resulting qubits. In the area of optical quantum computation, Mirrahimi et al. in [2] shows similar side-effect in a case of cat-qubits, that are applied in quantum photonic solutions by Xanadu [3]. The other photonic solutions using single photon sources or quantum dot as the entanglement supply is made by QuiX quantum [4].

In contrary, we plan to embed the qubits photonic space in higher dimension space intentionally, for avoiding the decoherence, especially dephasing and depolarization. We have described the possible implementation on quantum photonic chips in [5].

In this work we present the experiments on intentional imbedding of qubits in higher dimension spaces to create DFS qubits, on available quantum computers.

The implementation of DFS qubit

The goal of our work is to create two dimension DFS or a basis near to DFS, which means that the decoherence influence is very unlikely. The general pattern can be defined as follows. Let's take n qubits, which generates the 2^n dimension space. Then we take two states of such a space and we decide that one of them is a computational zero and the other one is computational one. The “bigger” space we call *Embedding Space* (ES) and the space, where the qubit exists – *Logic Space* (LS). The qubits that creates the ES we call *embedding qubits* and denote $|\psi\rangle_E$ and the resulting elements of LS – *logic qubits* and denote $|\psi\rangle_L$.

On the other hand, to define a qubit, we have to:

1. define what is the $|0\rangle_L$ and $|1\rangle_L$.
2. Define the set of basic one qubit gates, which can be used for defining the Universal, one qubit gate:

$$U(\theta, \lambda, \varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & -e^{-i\lambda} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\ e^{-i\varphi} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & e^{i(\lambda+\varphi)} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

3. Define the controlled negation gate, which is equivalence of entanglement.

The states that exist in the ES can be defined as: $|\psi\rangle_E = \sum_{j=0}^{2^n-1} \alpha_j |j\rangle_E$, where the basis states are $\{|j\rangle_E \in \mathcal{H}_E | j \in \{0, \dots, 2^n - 1\}\}$. In that case we define:

$$|0\rangle_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(|0\rangle_E^{\otimes n} + e^{i\delta} |1\rangle_E^{\otimes n} \right), |1\rangle_L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(|10\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}} + e^{i\delta} |01\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The state described by equation (2) is well-known GHZ state and we call it *constant state*, while the second one is the extension of $|\Psi^+\rangle$ Bell’s state and we call it *alternating state*. Hence, the logic state is represented by the whole set of embedding qubits that differs by the relative phase only.

The decoherence in the system appears if the external system, the environment that is not considered in computation, that is traditionally called *the Bath*, is coupled with the system by an entanglement. The whole system then, is described as follows: $|q_0 \dots q_{n-1}\rangle \otimes |b\rangle$, where $|q_k\rangle$ is k-th qubit and $|b\rangle$ is a bath.

Dephasing is such a type of decoherence that influences local phase shift in a system. In the perspective of ES qubits we can define it as the controlled-phase gate acting on the given qubit and a bath. Hence the system for the given eigen-state and bath is equal to superposition: $\lambda_j|q_0 \dots q_{n-1}0\rangle + e^{i\gamma_j}\lambda_j|q_0 \dots q_{n-1}1\rangle$, where $|q_0 \dots q_{n-1}\rangle = |j\rangle$, so j is binary representation of the number of the eigen-state, and λ_j is its original coordinate. Hence, the logical zero’s state after a bath acting is equal to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_E^{\otimes n} \otimes |0\rangle + e^{i(\delta+\gamma_2^{n-1})}|1\rangle_E^{\otimes n} \otimes |1\rangle)$. If we consider the state without bath (which can be done by tracing-out the density matrix), we obtain: $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_E^{\otimes n} + e^{i(\delta+\gamma_2^{n-1})}|1\rangle_E^{\otimes n})$, which still holds the condition for $|0\rangle_L$ - eq. (2). So, our logical zero is not vulnerable for dephasing influence. Similarly our logical one, when we repeat the same considerations.

Depolarization influences the optical system changing the polarization of photons in states. In non-optic based qubits its representation is as follows. The bath is now n qubit state $|b_0 \dots b_{n-1}\rangle$, and depolarization is $n - 1$ controlled X-Pauli gate, which influences k -th qubit of the system. In a case, the influence of depolarization depends on which qubit is affected.

nr	Logic zero $ 0\rangle_L$	Logic one $ 1\rangle_L$
0	$ 1\rangle_E^{\otimes n} + e^{i\delta} 0\rangle_E^{\otimes n}$	$ 10\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}} + e^{i\delta} 01\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}}$
n-1	$ 0\rangle_E^{\otimes n} + e^{i\delta} 1\rangle_E^{\otimes n}$	$ 01\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}} + e^{i\delta} 10\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n}{2}}$
k	$ 0\rangle_E^{\otimes k-1} 1\rangle 0\rangle_E^{\otimes n-k+1}$ $+ e^{i\delta} 1\rangle_E^{\otimes k-1} 0\rangle 1\rangle_E^{\otimes n-k+1}$	$ 01\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{k-1}{2}} 11\rangle 01\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n-k+1}{2}}$ $+ e^{i\delta} 10\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{k-1}{2}} 00\rangle 10\rangle_E^{\otimes \frac{n-k+1}{2}}$

Table 1. The influence of a bath on consecutive qubits for logic zero and one.

We see in the table 1 above, that influence of a bath for the first and last qubits holds its equation. For the remaining qubits bath’s influence generates destroys qubits, which means that the EM state becomes prohibited. However, we can detect this broken states in the measurement phase of computation. Hence our system is not fully Depolarization free however its influence is detectable, which is sufficient enough for computation.

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